

Utilization of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) Materials in Various Civil Engineering Works

Research Paper

Sandeep Sharma¹

¹* Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, ACET Amritsar, Punjab, India

*Corresponding Author's Email: sndpshrm63@gmail.com

*ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7915-6547>

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ABSTRACT

The effects of the addition of processed municipal solid wastes (MSW) materials on the engineering properties of M25 concrete and soft soils were investigated. For this, abandoned pile heads were collected and crushed into 20 mm sized aggregates. PVC waste, leather waste, nylon fiber cuttings, and iron waste were collected from nearby industries and pulverized to the required particle size. The processed waste materials were used as a replacement to conventional concrete aggregates. Many improvements have been observed in terms of slump, weight, and compressive strength of resultant concrete. However, leather waste was proved to be unsuccessful in improving any engineering property of concrete. Materials like cement kiln dust (CKD), Flyash, and Rice husk ash (RHA) were utilized for stabilizing subgrade and foundation soils. Significant improvements in strength were observed for stabilized soil samples. However, only CKD was proved successful in improving the compaction characteristics of the soil. Based on the study, waste like recycled aggregates, nylon cuttings, and iron waste are recommended to be used as a replacement to conventional aggregates for concrete. Also, municipal solid wastes like CKD, Flyash, and RHA are recommended to be used as soil stabilizers but their possible effects on human health should be taken care of in advance.

Keywords: *Municipal solid waste, recycled aggregates, slump, compressive strength, soil stabilizers, unconfined compressive strength*

INTRODUCTION

The world is passing through an era of urbanization and industrialization. Many infrastructure projects are being launched by the governments in every country. Simultaneously, numerous industrial units are being installed in almost every part of India as well. However, municipal authorities are facing huge difficulty in disposing of the industrial wastes/ construction debris being generated from these industries. Moreover, the existing dumpsites have also been running overloaded due to slow rate as well as poor technology available for recycling. This has made the issue of waste utilization a need of the hour.

Different types of waste materials are generated as a by-product of industrial operations and construction/ demolition activities. These materials can be utilized in various civil engineering works. In this study, different waste materials have been utilized to improve the engineering properties of cement concrete, pavement subgrades, and foundation soil. Coarse and fine aggregates in concrete were replaced with PVC waste, nylon fiber cuttings, iron waste, construction debris, and leather waste. Properties like weight, slump, workability, and compressive strength were determined for the resultant concrete blocks. On the other hand, materials like Rice husk ash (RHA), Fly ash, and Cement kiln dust (CKD) were used as additives to improve the properties of soft soils. Engineering

Corresponding Author's Affiliation:
Amritsar College of Engineering and Technology,
12 Km Stone, Amritsar-Jalandhar G.T Road,
Amritsar-143001 (Punjab), India

properties like shear strength and compressibility were assessed for the stabilized soil samples.

In the last two decades, several investigators have utilized these MSW materials to augment the properties of cement, concrete, and soil. Sikalidisa *et al.* (2002) suggested a methodology to prepare mortar from municipal solid waste. An extensive piece of work is done on recycled aggregates by Claudio and Antonio (2011). It was observed that the compressive strength of concrete from recycled aggregates is marginally less than that of concrete having conventional aggregates. However, durability was observed to be the same. Nassar and Soroushian (2012) utilized milled glass as a partial replacement for cement in concrete. Significant improvement in strength and durability was observed and this improvement was attributed to the formation of secondary calcium silicate hydrate. An extensive review of RCA was published by McNeil and Kang (2013). They observed a small decrease in values of compressive strength, modulus of rupture, and modulus of elasticity when conventional aggregates were replaced by recycled aggregates. However, a significant improvement in tensile strength was observed. Also, the performance of the structure is marginally affected by the replacement of natural aggregates with recycled ones. It was recommended by them to use recycled aggregates in concrete structures.

Stabilization is one of the oldest soil improvement techniques. It is being utilized since roman times. Dahale *et al.* (2012) published a review on soil stabilization. He concluded that utilization of waste materials in soil stabilization will not only solve the problem of waste disposal but will also provide new material alternatives. Moses and Saminu (2012) observed significant improvements in compaction and strength characteristics of black cotton soil when it was treated with CKD. Recently Pandey *et al.* (2013) have utilized lime, jute fiber, and Fly ash individually and in combination to stabilize black cotton soil. They observed that a combination of the three waste materials was much more efficient in

stabilizing black cotton soils as compared to the waste materials alone.

The purpose of this study was to see the effect of municipal solid wastes in improving the engineering properties of concrete and problematic soils. A better understanding of these characteristics will enhance the usage of these materials in construction works in places where they are in abundance. The study also focuses at the reduction of huge stockpiles of the various municipal solid wastes and their potential impact on human health.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Concrete and Solid Waste

a) Physical properties: The cement used was of 43 grade and its physical properties are reported in Table 1. Abandoned concrete pile heads were collected. These pile heads were crushed into 20 mm size particles and used as aggregates in concrete. In this paper, these aggregates are referred to as recycled aggregates. Waste leather was collected from nearby leather industries and it was pulverized to fine aggregates-sized particles. Similarly, pulverized PVC waste and iron waste were used as a replacement for fine aggregates. For iron waste, fineness modulus, specific gravity, and density were observed to be 2.65, 4.5, and 1.97 g/cc respectively. The density of nylon fiber cuttings was observed to be 1.13 g/cc. Physical properties of different aggregates are reported in Table 2. All the properties were determined in the laboratory as per the guidelines of IS codes (IS:383, 1970; IS:516, 1959; IS:1199, 1959).

b) Mix-design: Recycled aggregates were used to replace conventional aggregates in concrete. Three types of samples were prepared using 100%, 50%, and 25% recycled aggregates as replacements to conventional aggregates. PVC waste and leather wastes being non-earthen materials were used in small quantities. Fine aggregates were replaced by PVC waste and leather wastes in proportions of 5 and 10%. Iron waste was used as a replacement to fine aggregates in the proportion of 20%.

Table1: Physical Properties of 43- Grade Cement

Physical Properties	Observed Value
Specific Gravity	3.07
Fineness (%)	3.5
Standard Consistency (%)	34
Initial Setting Time (minutes)	45
Final Setting Time (minutes)	240
Soundness (mm)	2
28 days Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)	42.7

Table 2: Physical Properties of Materials Used as Aggregates

Physical Properties	Sand	Coarse Aggregates	Recycled Aggregates			Leather		PVC	
			100%	50%	25%	10%	5%	10%	5%
Specific Gravity	2.67	3.01	2.66	2.83	2.92	-	-	-	-
Water Absorption (%)	1.020	3.806	5.22	4.33	4.21	-	-	-	-
Moisture content (%)	0.155	0.806	0.6	0.703	0.75	-	-	-	-
Bulking (%)	2.48	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Fineness Modulus	2.715	7.36	8.19	7.27	7.57	2.82	2.632	7.213	7.28
Grading Zone	II	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Nylon fiber cuttings being light in weight were mixed in the proportion of 0.3%. The design mix for M25 concrete was determined as per the specifications of IS codes (IS:456, 2000; IS:10262, 1982). The details of various design mixes are reported in Table 3.

2. Soil and Solid Waste

Subgrade soil was procured from 1 m depth below ground level and foundation soil was collected beyond 1 m depth. CKD was collected from Jaypee Cement Plant, Solan, Himachal Pradesh Cement kiln dust (CKD) contains some chemicals which are injurious to human health. Therefore, exposure of CKD to groundwater should be avoided. The groundwater table in Kurukshetra is at 25 m depth below ground level. Hence CKD was selected as an additive to stabilize subgrade soil only. Rice husk ash was procured from Kohinoor food limited, G.T Road, Murthal, Haryana, and Fly ash was collected from Thermal power plant, Assandh village, Panipat, Haryana. Rice husk ash (RHA) and Fly ash were selected to stabilize foundation soils. The physical properties of materials are reported in Table 4. All the tests were conducted on statically compacted soil samples (Jain and Puri, 2013b).

ANALYSIS OF TEST RESULTS

1. Concrete

a) Weight of concrete: A significant decrease in the weight of concrete was observed when natural coarse aggregates were replaced with recycled aggregate. For plain cement concrete (PCC) weight was observed to be 7.92 kg. However, a lower range of weights was observed for concrete in which the natural aggregates were replaced with waste material. For concrete having recycled aggregates (RA) as constituents, weight ranges from 7.53 kg to 7.78 kg. This can be attributed to the lower specific gravity of recycled aggregates. Also, a decreasing trend was observed for concrete in which fine aggregates were replaced with PVC waste, iron waste, and leather wastes. In the case of PVC concrete weight ranges from 7.65 kg to 7.87 kg and for leather concrete it ranges from 6.27 kg to 7.08 kg. Hence lightweight concrete can be designed by

replacing natural aggregates with suitable waste materials.

b) Slump: A decreasing trend was observed in the values of slump when natural aggregates were replaced by waste materials. For plain cement, the concrete value of the slump was observed to be 94 mm. Values of slump decrease from 86 mm to 78 mm for concrete in which coarse aggregates were replaced with recycled aggregate. For leather concrete slump ranges from 79 mm to 82 mm. A decrease in weight was observed with an increase in the percentage of pulverized leather. However, in the case of PVC concrete slump increases from 91 mm to 92 mm with an increase in the percentage of PVC. Similarly, a decreasing trend in the values of the slump was observed for concrete having iron waste and nylon fibre cuttings.

Observed values of the slump for a combination of 20% iron waste and 0.3% nylon fibre cuttings, 20% iron waste alone and 0.3% nylon fibre cuttings alone were observed as 75mm, 88mm and 80 mm respectively. Better workability was observed in the case of PVC concrete as compared to the concrete having other wastes aggregates as constituents. This decreasing trend in workability can be attributed to the higher absorption capacity of waste materials.

c) Compressive strength: Several cubes ($a = 150$ mm) were prepared and were tested for compressive strength as per the specifications of IS codes [8, 9]. The average 28 days compressive strength of M25 PCC was observed to be 28.72 kN/m². When conventional aggregates were replaced with recycled aggregates in proportions of 100% to 25% the average compressive strength increased from 31.28 kN/m² to 33.14 kN/m². The achieved higher strength can be attributed to better bonding between recycled aggregates and conventional aggregates.

When fine aggregates were replaced PVC waste in proportions of 10% to 5% the average compressive strength varies from 26.76 kN/m² to 28.87 kN/m².

Table3: Details of Design Mix Calculations

Type of concrete	Mix Design			
	Water (Litre)	Cement (kg)	Sand (kg)	Coarse Aggregates (kg)
PCC	0.46	1	1.34	2.86
100% Recycled Aggregates	0.59	1	1.34	2.48
50% Recycled Aggregates	0.58	1	1.34	2.67
25% Recycled Aggregates	0.58	1	1.34	2.75
5% PVC	0.46	1	1.34	2.86
10% PVC	0.46	1	1.34	2.86
5% Leather Waste	0.46	1	1.34	2.86
10% Leather Waste	0.46	1	1.34	2.86
20% Iron waste	0.53	1	1.18	2.22
20% Iron waste + 0.3% Nylon fiber cuttings	0.53	1	1.18	2.22
0.3% Nylon fiber cuttings	0.53	1	1.18	2.22

Table 4: Physical Properties of Soil and Materials

Physical Properties	Materials				
	Foundation Soil	Subgrade Soil	Cement kiln dust	Rice husk ash	Fly ash
Gravel (%)	0	-	-	0	0
Sand (%)	6.75	-	100	23.22	7.5
Clay + silt (%)	93.25	100	-	76.78	92.5
Specific gravity	2.48	2.36	2.52	1.95	2.09
Shrinkage Limit	36.52	-	-	-	-
Liquid limit	54	45	NP		
Plastic limit	25	22		NP	NP
Plasticity index	29	23			
Is classification	CH	CI	SM	ML	ML
OMC (%)	14.71	18	-	-	-
MDD (g/cc)	1.93	1.69	-	-	-

However, PVC concrete has shown lower strength in comparison with PCC but the characteristic strength was still achieved. This can be attributed to poor bonding between fine aggregate and PVC waste.

When fine aggregates were replaced leather waste in proportions of 10% to 5% the average compressive strength varies from 0.938 kN/m² to 9.07 kN/m². Less than one-third of characteristic strength was achieved in this case. This can be attributed to the negligible bonding between leather waste and fine aggregates.

Higher strengths were observed when 20% iron waste and 0.3% nylon wastes were used alone as well as in combination with other ingredients in concrete. In this case, 28 days strength varies from 34.21 kN/m² to 37.92 kN/m². This can be attributed to higher individual strengths of iron waste and nylon fibre cuttings. The variation of compressive strength with the age of concrete is shown in Figure 1.

2. Soil

a) Shrinkage Characteristics: Shrinkage limit tests were conducted on foundation soil samples stabilized with Fly ash and Rice husk ash (RHA) (IS:2720-Part 6, 1972). The effect of these municipal solid wastes on the shrinkage of foundation soil was observed to be insignificant. However, a general increase in shrinkage limit from 36.52 % to 43 % was observed as the percentage of RHA increased from 5% to 25%. However, a small decrease in the value of shrinkage limit from 36.52 % to 35.65 % was observed for soil stabilized with fly ash. Reduction in shrinkage can be attributed to the reactions between soil and free lime content of RHA. Variation between shrinkage limit and percentage of additive is shown in Figure 2.

b) Compaction Characteristics: Standard Proctor tests have been conducted to determine optimum moisture content (OMC) and maximum dry density (MDD) of both soils stabilized with various percentages of Fly ash, Rice husk ash (RHA), and Cement kiln dust (CKD) (IS:2720-Part 7, 1974).

Values of MDD and OMC for foundation soil have been observed as 1.93 g/cc and 14.91 % respectively. For subgrade soil, MDD and OMC have been observed as 1.69 g/cc and 18 %. It has been observed that MDD increases from 1.682 g/cc to 1.768 g/cc and OMC decreases from 19 % to 15 % when subgrade soil was stabilized with CKD. This can be attributed to the cement content present in CKD. However, an opposite trend has been observed for foundation soil stabilized with Fly ash and RHA. For Fly ash, stabilized samples, MDD decreases from 1.8 g/cc to 1.77 g/cc as the percentage of Fly ash increases. But OMC increases from 12.9 % to 22.5 % with an increase in the percentage of Fly ash. Similarly, for RHA stabilized samples, MDD decreases from 1.81 g/cc to 1.54 g/cc as the percentage of RHA increases. But OMC increases from 19.4 % to 30.23 % with an increase in the percentage of RHA. This can be attributed to the lower specific gravity and high absorption capacity of Fly ash and RHA. The variation of MDD and OMC with the percentage of additive is shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

c) Strength Parameters: Unconfined compressive strength tests were performed in order to determine strength characteristics of soils stabilized with various municipal solid wastes (IS:2720-Part 10, 1973). Values for shear strength of foundation soil and subgrade soil have been observed as 3.357 N/cm² and 0.85 N/cm² respectively. It has been observed that the shear strength of subgrade soil stabilized with CKD increases from 0.85 N/cm² to 2.9 N/cm² with an increase in the percentage of CKD. Shear strength of foundation soil stabilized with Fly ash increases from 3.36 N/cm² to 3.65 N/cm² with an increase in the percentage of Fly ash. Similarly, the Shear strength of foundation soil stabilized with RHA increases from 3.36 N/cm² to 3.85 N/cm² with an increase in the percentage of RHA. This increase in the shear strength of soil can be attributed to the reactions between soil and free lime content of these solid wastes. Significant improvements in other engineering properties have also been reported by various authors (Jain and Puri, 2013a). Variation of UCS with the percentage of

additive for different soil samples is shown in Figure 5.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results, following conclusions have been drawn:

1. Recycled aggregates are better alternatives to conventional coarse aggregates. A significant increase in the compressive strength of concrete has been observed in the case of recycled aggregates, iron waste, and nylon fiber cuttings. However, a lower slump has been observed in these cases. It is recommended to use admixtures for improving the workability of resultant concrete.
2. Municipal solid wastes like PVC waste, nylon fiber cuttings, and steel scrap can only be used in small quantities because of their lower specific gravities and incompatibility with earthen materials. Also, resistance against fire is not assured for concrete having these wastes as constituents.
3. Leather waste should not be used as a replacement for conventional aggregates.
4. It is recommended by authors to use CKD as a stabilizer for problematic soil at shallow depths and rice husk ash for soils beyond shallow depths.
5. These industrial wastes do consist of harmful chemicals, their exposure to the human atmosphere and groundwater table must be avoided.

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Fig 1: Compressive Strength (kN/m²) Vs Age of Concrete

Fig. 2: Shrinkage Limit Vs Percentage of Additive

Fig. 3: MDD Vs Percentage of Additive

Fig.4: OMC Vs Percentage of Additive

Fig.5: UCS Vs Percentage of Additive

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